

Project number: 874662
Project Acronym: HEAP

Project Title: Human Exposome Assessment Platform

Project website URL:

Project Coordinator: Joakim Dillner

Organization: KI

E-mail: Joakim.Dillner@ki.se

Work Package 4
Consumer Cohort

Work package Leader: Frederik Trier Møller

Organization: Statens Serum Institut

E-Mail: frtm@ssi.dk

Project Deliverable

D4.1: Secure platform and recruitment

Deliverable due date: 2022-12-31

Deliverable due month: M36

Document history

Version	Date	Changes	By	Reviewed
0.1	2022-12-07	First draft	Frederik Trier Møller, Caroline Ewes, Bartłomiej Wilkowski, Steven Chong, Thor Grønberg Junker	Frederik Trier Møller
0.1	2022-12-20	Small corrections	Roxana Merino	Frederik Trier Møller
1.0	2022-12-22	Final version	Frederik Trier Møller	Frederik Trier Møller Joakim Dillner

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides documentation about the development and use of the platform to collect consumer purchase data. This document briefly describes the frontend functionality, architecture, data flows, and planned updates. It also describes the current recruitment status, reasons for the lower-than-expected recruitment, and initiatives to mitigate this. It highlights tools for product enrichment developed to date and the current plans to publish papers describing them and make them available to the research community. Thus deliverable 4.1 addresses objective 1, the recruitment of 10.000 participants, using the framework that secures user privacy to collect household electronic receipts data, and allows for informed consent.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1 Introduction	5
2 Work progress and unexpected risks.	6
3 Description of the platform to collect consumer data	6
4 Evaluation of platform	8
5 Adaptations to the platform	8
6 Recruitment status	8
7 Data annotation validation and enrichment	10
8 Contributions from partners	12
9 Summary	12
10 References	14

1 Introduction

WP4 aims to explore the feasibility of using consumer purchase data to continuously model and assess the household consumed exposomes impact on health, and to use results to develop lifestyle communication models supporting lasting habit change.

Consumer purchase data are available to consumers through loyalty and credit card-based solutions in several EU countries. The legislation in Denmark enables the collection and use of personal non-anonymized consumer data, provided informed consent.

SSI has developed an electronic E-consent solution (in collaboration with KI) that allows citizens to transfer consumer data from private receipt providers to research.

WP4 recruits participants from a Danish commercial e-receipt provider which is used by more than 1.1 million Danes. The e-receipts platform allows consumer data collection from 3 of the four largest retail chains.

Deliverable 4.1 addresses objective 1, the recruitment of participants, using the framework to collect household electronic receipts data, secures user privacy, and allows for informed consent. The goal is to recruit 10000 participants.

The next sections describe the platform used to collect consumer data, including planned updates due to technical changes in the Danish digital signature system. In addition, this deliverable describes the recruitment status, measures to increase recruitment and mitigate the effects of slow recruitment. Finally, D4.1 analyses the impact of the work on the scientific output of the project.

2 Work progress and unexpected risks.

The Covid-19 pandemic coincided with the start of the HEAP project and caused considerable delay. SSI is a preparedness institute, and most SSI resources were directed towards handling the pandemic. Apart from low access to personnel, covid-19 related work tasks caused bottlenecks.

HEAP Resource utilisation was adjusted to the situation, and from the beginning of 2021, there was good progress.

Work on the landing page was finalised, Project data collection was approved by authorities, finalising institutional DPIA. FAQ, backend, API access, data management and storage, external security checks, penetrations tests, risk mapping etc. were finalised. On the 8th of June, a pilot study of the fully functional solution was conducted, and minor adjustments were made based on user input from 10 pilot users. On the 23rd of June 2021, the electronic consumer receipts collection solution at mineindkob.dk was launched, and recruitment for the mypurchases cohort commenced, with an approximately one-year delay. Since the 23rd of June 2021 management and collection of user input have been the main tasks, in addition to a minor adjustment to the platform in the fall of 2021. In the second half of 2022, it became clear that a new version of the platform was needed to accommodate a change in the two-factor authentication system due to a change in provider and technical solution concerning the Danish national digital system.

3 Description of the platform to collect consumer data

The e-consent solution consists of a landing page with an e-consent form. Citizens sign with a two-factor authentication system (Danish national NemID system), Securing Personal Identification Number and contact information from digital receipts providers. Through integration with Storeboxs consumer data API, the data transfer is verified by the citizens through a validation loop. Consumer data, including historical consumer data, is continuously collected but may be discontinued at any time by the citizen. The platform has had a runtime of above 99% since its launch.

Figure 3.1 Overview of system setup

The latest version of the page can be explored at mineindkob.dk or mineindkob.ssi.dk. Further details have previously been provided in D13.4.

Figure 3.2 frontend example

Dine indkøb
Styrker sundheden

Supported by | Withdraw Consent | Registration | Receipt Page

English | Dansk

Supported by | Researchers | News | publication | Cont

Supported by

Research

How this Study Works

Information about registration

Frequently asked questions

Would you like to help combat diseases such as salmonella, IBD, and other complex diseases every time you shop for groceries?

Registration

Supported by;

EHEN project HEAP
The project is supported by EU Horizon 2020.
Through the project HEAP: <https://heap-exposome.eu/> grant agreement No. 874662. part of the European Human Exposome Network <https://www.humanexposome.eu/>

4 Evaluation of platform

Participant input was collected since the platform's launch using a dedicated and secure email and phone number. An internal report (in Danish) evaluating the first three months was produced, and minor changes to the text and design were made, the latter to improve readability on android. Otherwise, the main inputs from participants were that the text was on the long side. Collected user input was used to improve the user experience in the adapted platform, as described below.

5 Adaptations to the platform

The Danish national digital signature solution NemID is changed to MitID. As the page originally developed with KI does not support the new MitID solution and has challenges concerning responsiveness on android devices, an updated version of the consent solution is being developed at SSI. The page and text will also get a redesign expected to improve recruitment, due to a more simplified recruitment process. The transition to the updated page will not affect the already collected consent from current participants, but they will be informed of the change, provided they have given consent to receive updates. The new version of the landing page will contain the same elements but will be optimised based on collected user input and more in line with other digital solutions originating from SSI.

6 Recruitment status

On the 23rd of June, the electronic consumer receipts collection solution was launched. To date, more than 400 participants have been recruited, which is lower than the target of more than 10000 participants. The main reason for this lower recruitment, apart from the initial delay, is the arrival of New Covid-variants in 2021, where personnel resource bottlenecks have delayed planned recruitment initiatives, and the previously described delays relating to compliance bottlenecks in the first year of the pandemic. In addition, general untargeted recruitment directly from the Storebox app users (via a link where participants could participate) proved to recruit fewer citizens than anticipated. It was a risk from the beginning as we still needed to learn how willing patients and citizens would be to participate in the study. We hope to recruit thousands of patients and citizens over the next year. We explain to participants that studying their data will improve our understanding of diseases and healthy lifestyles, which will benefit them. We have made great efforts to ensure that the consent model allows consumers to give specific consent for the projects in which they

would like to participate. We also provide clear assurances to participants that their data will be stored de-identified on a secure IT infrastructure, their contact information will be stored on a separate server, and to ensure confidentiality, the same person will not have access to both identification and research data.

Currently, some measures to improve recruitment are planned or already in place.

1. The updated landing page will include more graphical content and an updated look following the SSI main page design. This will provide further reassurance to participants and improve recruitment.
2. The project will continue collaboration with other Danish institutions such as the greater capital region of Copenhagen, where patients newly diagnosed with inflammatory bowel diseases, as part of the creation of a new inception cohort (PROGNOSIS study), are invited to provide consumer data in addition to a broad range of biological materials [1]). Although the expected impact on recruitment will continue to be modest, the data collected will be highly informative due to the nature of the collected data from the participants in Prognosis. As the study involves biological data collection, it is approved by the regional IRB, as reported in WP13.
3. As a response to the Covid-19 crisis, a study is conducted on how consumer purchase data may be used to analyse changes in relation to Covid-19 infection as part of a Danish initiative to study the late effects of Covid-19 (AFTER COVID study) [2]. As with the PROGNOSIS study, consumer data is an extra research option for participants, and include a link to the consumer cohort in the fourth questionnaire the participants receive. Thus some research (and covid-19) fatigue may have affected the recruitment from this data source, although continued recruitment is expected.

To date, recruitment has been passive because CPD is an opt-in possibility in the studies mentioned above. In 2023 WP4 aims to commence targeted recruitment via dedicated invitation letters in an already established cohort and among danish citizens previously affected by food-borne infections such as salmonella.

1. The first initiative includes targeted recruitment among persons affected by food-borne diseases such as salmonella. A new member of the project group (Caroline Ewes) will run this recruitment of persons with a previous salmonella infection.

2. The second initiative aims to initiate recruitment among participants in the “Bedre Sundhed I Generationer” cohort BSIG (Danish National Birth Cohort)[3]. The recruitment is conditional on final approval from the BSIG governing board. Input to this decision is provided through a focus group and a brief questionnaire concerning the projected invitation to the mypurchases cohort, aimed at BSIG and user panels. This also addresses a remark made in deliverable D2.2 concerning the need for increased participant involvement. Finally, it constitutes a collaborative effort within EHEN as BSIG is already part of the EHEN through the ATHLETE project.

Collaboration

Even if the recruitment efforts above continue to be less successful than anticipated, we expect a close collaboration with another Danish consumer cohort, using almost the same consumer data source (cost neutral). It will help WP4 meet its goals. Collaborating with another Danish cohort and recruiting participants from Storebox is expected to enable joint research using data from +10000 participants. A PhD student from this project is currently visiting SSI. Joint publications are expected[4]. The collaboration enables the SMIL cohort data analysis using the data enrichment pipeline developed in HEAP, expected to be submitted for publication in early 2023.

7 Data annotation validation and enrichment

The collected data are generally as expected and consist of the data depicted in table 7.1.

A key feature of the data collected is that many participants have consumer purchase data originating as far back as 2014. Thus catch-up recruitment may allow us to identify longitudinal patterns between consumer exposures and health-related outcomes.

The main scientific work has focused on establishing a general-purpose pipeline to enrich the data. The pipeline enables product characterization and matching to Openfoodfacts, kemiluppen, FRIDA, and GS1 using direct matching and text mining techniques, enabling the identification of exposure to nutrients, chemicals, and additives.

Table 7.1 consumer purchase data collected.

name	label	description	example values
receipt ID	receipt ID	receipt ID	Receipt_3773
itemname	description of product from receipt	description of product from receipt	Banana
itemnumber	itemnumber or GTIN13/EAN/UPC	itemnumber or GTIN13/EAN/UPC can be linked to other existing data sources with established metadata	5710815000014
amount	number of items bought	number of items bought	1
itemprice	price in dkk	price in dkk	12.95
rabat	discount	discount in dkk	-1.00
purchdate	date of purchase	date of purchase	02-01-2021
weekno	weekno	week of purchase	5
monthno	monthno	month of purchase	2
yearno	yearno	year of purchase	2021
merchantname	name of merhcant	name of merchant	supermarket name

Preliminary results from the enrichment of data from kemiluppen (as consumer chemistry database Provided by the Danish Consumer Council)

were presented at the EHEN meeting in May 2022, and at the HEAP symposium in June 2022.

Together with a description of the platform to collect data, the results of applying the pipeline to real-life consumer purchases, and assessing the external exposome from consumer purchases, are to be submitted to a peer-reviewed journal in early 2023, with contributions from WP2 and WP7 and several partner institutions. The pipeline with simulated example data will be available in the HEAP platform Hopsworks (WP6) and on GitHub.

The work toward identifying longitudinal patterns between consumer exposures and health-related outcomes (SSI) is delayed due to reduced recruitment and the covid-19 pandemic, as explained above. However, the main research targets remain unchanged.

8 Contributions from partners

MLCF and KI have provided valuable advice and support throughout the process.

Apart from contributions to the planned paper focusing on product enrichment, the other WP4 partners will contribute next year, enabling the pipeline to run in Hopsworks and conducting joint analytical work.

Further, the internal SSI DPIA provided information to deliverable D2.2, and joint publications are planned.

A short technical description of the CPD enrichment pipeline is part of deliverable 6.2.

9 Summary

The framework to collect household electronic receipts data is now in place. Work on the landing page is finished, and project data collection was approved by authorities, finalising the institutional DPIA. FAQ, backend, API access, data management and storage, external security checks, penetrations tests, risk mapping etc., have also been finalised, with expert help from WP2. We thus successfully commenced recruitment using a secure electronic customer receipts analysis platform, as detailed in the work plan. As a result of the initial delay due to the covid-19 crisis and less-than-expected passive recruitment, recruitment still needs to meet the target to date. Recruitment has however been ongoing since June 2022, and more than 400 participants have been recruited to date.

Currently, a number of measures to improve recruitment are planned or already in place.

Apart from the graphical and functional update to the landing page and recruitment flow, passive options are continued. For instance:

- Recruitment from the digital receipts providers app.
- Continues collaboration with the greater capital region of Copenhagen on the inception cohort (PROGNOSIS study)
- Recruitment as part of a Danish initiative to study the late effects of Covid-19 (after covid).
- In 2023, WP4 aims to commence targeted recruitment via dedicated invitation letters in an already established cohort and among danish citizens previously affected by food-borne infections such as salmonella.
- Increase collaboration with other Danish cohorts also recruiting participants from Storebox, which is expected to enable joint research using data from +10000 participants even if the above initiatives should not prove successful.

Even if the recruitment effort continues to be less successful than anticipated, we expect a close collaboration with other Danish consumer cohorts, using almost the same consumer data source (cost neutral), to help WP4 meet the goals. A PhD student has joined the HEAP team at SSI, for three months from 1/11-2022 to support this effort. The collaboration enables analysis of the SMIL cohort data using a data enrichment pipeline developed in HEAP.

Despite delays, we expect the final research output to be as detailed in the proposal, primarily as a number of the first 400 participants provide data spanning several years in some instances as far back as 2014.

The main scientific work has focused on establishing a pipeline to enrich the data. The pipeline enables product characterisation and matching to Openfoodfacts, kemiluppen, FRIDA, and GS1 using direct matching and text mining techniques, enabling the identification of exposure to nutrients, chemicals, and additives.

Together with a description of the platform to collect data, the results of applying the pipeline to real-life consumer purchases will be submitted to a peer-reviewed journal in early 2023 with contributions from WP2, WP7 and several HEAP partner institutions. Later in 2023 the work toward identifying longitudinal patterns between consumer exposures and health-related outcomes including chronic diseases and covid-19 will commence.

10 References

- 1) Attauabi M, Madsen GR, Bendtsen F, Wewer AV, Wilkens R, Ilvemark J, et al. Influence of Genetics, Immunity and the Microbiome on the Prognosis of Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD Prognosis Study): the protocol for a Copenhagen IBD Inception Cohort Study. *BMJ Open*. 2022;12(6):e055779.
- 2) Sørensen, A.I.V., Spiliopoulos, L., Bager, P. et al. A nationwide questionnaire study of post-acute symptoms and health problems after SARS-CoV-2 infection in Denmark. *Nat Commun* 13, 4213 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-31897-x>
- 3) <https://www.dnbc.dk/about-the-dnbc> Better health for mother and child - the Danish National Birth Cohort (DNBC), its structure, history and aims. Olsen J, Meder IK. *Norsk Epidemiologi* 2014; 24(1-2): 37-38
- 4) Sørensen KK, Nielsen EP, Møller AL, Andersen MP, Møller FT, Melbye M, et al. Food purchases in households with and without diabetes based on consumer purchase data. *Prim Care Diabetes*. 2022;16(4):574-80.